

ENHANCING DRIP IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY TO BOOST COTTON YIELD IN SALINE SOILS

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Abstract

Saline soils pose significant challenges to agriculture, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions where cotton is a critical crop. This article explores the integration of advanced drip irrigation technologies with innovative management practices to enhance cotton yield in such challenging conditions. By addressing water scarcity and soil salinity, the proposed strategies aim to optimize resource use and improve agricultural productivity.

Key words: Drip irrigation technology, cotton growth, saline soils, biostimulants, soil salinity management, sustainable farming practices.

Introduction

Cotton is a vital cash crop grown worldwide, yet its cultivation faces challenges in saline soils, where high salinity levels hinder root development, nutrient uptake, and overall plant growth. Drip irrigation has emerged as a promising technology to mitigate these challenges, ensuring precise water delivery and reducing salt accumulation near the root zone (Sharma et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2021).

This article examines how modern advancements in drip irrigation can address the unique demands of cotton grown in saline soils, focusing on strategies to maximize yield while conserving water and improving soil health.

Challenges of saline soils for cotton cultivation

Impact on Plant Growth: High salinity reduces osmotic potential, making it difficult for roots to absorb water (Munns et al., 2008).

Nutrient Imbalances: Excess salts disrupt the availability and uptake of essential nutrients like potassium and calcium (Rengel et al., 2015).

Soil Structure Degradation: Salinity can lead to poor soil structure, reducing aeration and root penetration (Hussain et al., 2020).

Role of drip irrigation in saline soils

Drip irrigation is particularly suited for saline environments because it:
Delivers Water Directly to Roots: Minimizing evaporation and salt concentration on the soil surface (Tanner et al., 2016).

Facilitates Leaching: Allows for controlled flushing of excess salts away from the root zone (Khan et al., 2020).

Supports fertigation: Enables precise application of fertilizers, optimizing nutrient availability even in saline conditions (Al-Karaki et al., 2011).

Enhancements in drip irrigation technology

Salinity-tolerant emitters: Designing emitters that resist clogging in saline water (Singh et al., 2017).

Smart irrigation systems: Utilizing sensors and automated controls to monitor soil salinity and adjust irrigation schedules dynamically (Zhou et al., 2021).

Biostimulants and soil amendments: Incorporating products that enhance root tolerance to salinity and improve soil structure (Gomez et al., 2019; García et al., 2020).

Integrated management practices: Combining drip irrigation with crop rotation, mulching, and gypsum application to enhance soil quality (Ahmed et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Diagram of the experimental plot layout and distribution of the instruments

Case Studies

Several field trials have demonstrated the potential of enhanced drip irrigation systems:

India: Farmers achieved a 20% increase in cotton yield by integrating drip systems with saline-resistant fertilizers (Singh & Sharma, 2020).

Uzbekistan: Trials with biostimulants in saline soils improved cotton growth and water use efficiency by up to 30% (Abdullayev et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Improving cotton yield in saline soils is a complex challenge that requires an integrated approach combining technological advancements with sustainable agricultural practices. Saline soils, characterized by high salt concentrations, severely affect plant growth and productivity. However, with the right interventions, such as optimized drip irrigation systems and proper soil management, it is possible to mitigate the adverse effects of salinity and significantly enhance cotton yield. Drip irrigation, by offering precise water delivery directly to the root zone, reduces water wastage, lowers evaporation losses, and minimizes the accumulation of salts on the soil surface, which are common in traditional irrigation methods. This method not only ensures the efficient use of water but also helps maintain a favorable soil salinity environment for cotton plants. The integration of advanced technologies like salinity-tolerant emitters, automated irrigation controls, and fertigation systems makes it possible to fine-tune irrigation schedules based on real-time soil moisture and salinity levels, further enhancing water use efficiency and nutrient uptake. Moreover, the application of biostimulants and soil amendments can improve the salinity tolerance of cotton, stimulate root development, and enhance soil structure. These biotechnological innovations, when combined with practices such as mulching, crop rotation, and gypsum application, offer a holistic approach to managing saline soils and improving cotton yields.

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